

Artificial intelligence in occupational health practice

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Abstract

This viewpoint delves into the transformative role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in occupational medicine, highlighting its profound impact on preventive healthcare. AI's integration into various aspects of occupational health is reshaping diagnostics, risk assessment, and healthcare administration. The paper emphasizes AI's learning, planning, reasoning, and problem-solving capabilities, which are pivotal in enhancing diagnostic accuracy for conditions like occupational tumor detection and long-term health effects from exposure to low-level hazards of chemicals. AI may be valuable for monitoring workplace health and safety, employing predictive analytics for early risk detection, and preventing occupational injuries and work-related diseases. In this viewpoint, the authors explore AI's role in managing health data through natural language processing, aiding physicians in clinical documentation and patient communication. It is needed to address ethical challenges related to AI implementation in the healthcare sector and occupational health practice, such as data protection and decision-making accountability. In conclusion, AI may expand worker training and health literacy scope, demonstrating its comprehensive utility in fostering a safer, healthier, and more informed workforce in occupational health settings.

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Take-home message: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing occupational medicine by enhancing diagnostics and risk assessment while facing ethical data protection and decision-making challenges. Its application is key to improving workplace safety and health literacy and fostering a well-informed workforce.

Key-words: artificial intelligence; occupational health and safety; workplace.

INTRODUCTION

As Artificial Intelligence (AI) permeates various sectors, its transformative impact on occupational medicine, particularly in enhancing preventive healthcare measures, is becoming increasingly significant. AI is redefining the capabilities in various aspects of daily life, with a predicted substantial influence over the next 5–10 years. At the same time, occupational medicine will have to be ready to face the social and economic changes induced by AI, which will significantly impact the workforce. We can imagine that in the near future, AI could provide occupational doctors with the possibility of creating precision medicine in the workplace, for example, by identifying genetic defects that favor the onset of occupational diseases [1,2].

This possibility makes us understand that a profound debate will be necessary between experts in the discipline and society's social and political forces because it will be necessary to understand to what extent risk prediction is truly health protection and where it becomes discrimination [3]. This debate arose many years ago, at the beginning of the applications of genetics; today is the time for it to come to life. At the same time, AI will bring significant transformations in the economy and society, and the occupational doctor will have to grasp the consequences of these transformations in the workforce.

This article aims to explore the specific applications of AI in occupational medicine, a branch of healthcare primarily focused on prevention, and its role in mitigating workplace-related injuries and diseases.

DISCUSSION

AI's proficiency in learning, planning, reasoning, and problem-solving is pivotal in occupational medicine, particularly for occupational physicians who safeguard workers' health against long-term exposure to low-level chemicals or carcinogens. AI enhances diagnostic accuracy and efficiency in identifying health conditions, including tumor detection and treatment planning [4,5]. This precision is crucial in detecting long-term health effects that are otherwise challenging to ascertain.

In workplace health and safety, AI is vital for monitoring and detecting early risk and preventing occupational injuries and diseases. Occupational health and safety professionals leverage AI-powered tools for comprehensive health risk assessments and workplace condition monitoring. Predictive analytics, a facet of AI, is essential in preemptively identifying accidents and occupational disease risks [6].

Furthermore, the integration of AI in healthcare administration revolutionizes resource management, streamlines processes, and enhances care planning [7,8]. In occupational medicine, AI's role in managing and analyzing health data, particularly through natural language processing, optimizes clinical documentation and patient communication [8].

The utility of AI in occupational medicine extends to the epidemiological analysis of data from medical examinations. This analysis is invaluable for physicians assessing the effectiveness of employer-implemented prevention and protection measures. Such AI-driven epidemiological insights guide the risk assessment process and the development of targeted interventions to mitigate identified health risks.

AI's efficiency in processing and analyzing large volumes of health data allows occupational physicians to deeply understand health trends and risks within a workforce. This understanding informs recommendations for improving workplace safety and health policies.

However, implementing AI in healthcare, including occupational medicine, raises ethical concerns such as decision-making accountability and data protection [9]. Addressing these challenges is crucial to ensure data privacy and accuracy. Much more problematic, as we have mentioned, is the ethical dilemma between protecting the worker's health and protecting the right to work. The employer, the worker, and society have vested interests in this problem; reconciling them requires a multidisciplinary commitment. In Italy, the La.R.A. study group has long been committed to defining the aspects of collective ethics derived from these conditions. It is hoped that his activity continues to address these increasingly complex issues [10].

AI will bring about profound societal change in numerous sectors. From an employment point of view, the first result of the new technologies will be the disappearance from the market of those still operating with the old technologies. Millions of workers performing the tasks of today's information technology will have to reskill their skills, or they will lose their jobs. It must be recognized that the practice of occupational medicine has not been quick enough to understand that the health problems of information technologies are not the visual disturbances or neck pain of the video terminal operator but the complex series of sensorial and psychosocial stimuli imposed by new technologies, which only a few occupational doctors have noticed in a timely manner [11]. AI will rapidly transform the workforce and pose new challenges to prevention operators.

AI is also expanding into worker training and health literacy, transforming workers' health literacy and self-care education. AI-driven health information accessible through digital devices enhances knowledge acquisition, access, comprehension, and application of health information [12]. This approach narrows the gap between healthcare providers and workers, making medical information more accessible and understandable.

CONCLUSIONS

AI's role in occupational medicine and workplace health and safety management is increasingly prominent. It provides powerful tools for diagnostics, healthcare resource management, and workplace safety while necessitating careful navigation

of ethical and practical challenges. AI's advancements are integral to fostering a safer, healthier, and more informed workforce, marking a significant leap in occupational health practice. The versatility of AI in occupational health is evident in its application across various domains, including training, health literacy, and even managing compensation claims in some countries. The social and economic changes brought by new technologies will profoundly transform society. Occupational doctors will, as always, be on the front line to recognize and monitor these changes.

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References

1. Magnavita N, Sabatelli M, Scoditti E, Chirico F. Personalized prevention in mercury-induced amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: a case report. *Appl Sci.* 2020;10:7839. doi:10.3390/app10217839.
2. Magnavita N, Chirico F. New and emerging risk factors in Occupational Health. *Appl Sci.* 2020;10(4):8906. doi: 10.3390/app10248906.
3. Magnavita N. *Biotechnologie e condizioni di lavoro.* Roma: Edizioni Lavoro; 1989.
4. Davenport TH, Glaser J. Just-in-time delivery comes to knowledge management. *Harv Bus Rev.* 2002 Jul;80(7):107-111.
5. Fakoor R, Ladhak F, Nazi A, Huber M. Using deep learning to enhance cancer diagnosis and classification. *Proceedings of the 30th International Conference on Machine Learning, Atlanta, Georgia, USA; 2013.*
6. Williams N. Artificial Intelligence in Occupational Health. *Occup Med.* 2023;73(7):449. <https://doi.org/10.1093/occmed/kqad040>.
7. Hanefi Calp M. Use of Deep Learning Approaches in Cancer Diagnosis. In: Kose U, Alzubi J. (eds) *Deep Learning for Cancer Diagnosis. Studies in Computational Intelligence*, vol 908. Singapore: Springer; 2021. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-6321-8_15.
8. Al Kuwaiti A, Nazer K, Al-Reedy A, Al-Shehri S, Al-Muhanna A, Subbarayalu AV, et al. A Review of the Role of Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare. *J Pers Med.* 2023 Jun 5;13(6):951. doi: 10.3390/jpm13060951.
9. Char DS, Shah NH, Magnus D. Implementing Machine Learning in Health Care - Addressing Ethical Challenges. *N Engl J Med.* 2018 Mar 15;378(11):981-983. doi: 10.1056/NEJMp1714229.
10. Magnavita N, De Lorenzo G, Sacco A. Hazardous workers and risk for third parties. The advocacy action of the La.R.A. Group. In "Case-book on Advocacy in Public Health", Parker L & Hernández I (Eds). Geneva: World Federation of Public Health Associations (WFPHA); 2021. Available from: <https://www.halksagligiokulu.org/Kitap/DownloadEBook/ada0d097-1b52-43d0-bf4c-f569751aec2b>. Accessed on 30 December 2023.
11. Magnavita N. *Vivere in ufficio. Manuale per la prevenzione dei rischi nel lavoro d'ufficio.* Roma; Edizioni Lavoro; 1990. ISBN 88-7910-468-3.
12. Nejhaddadgar N, Darabi F, Chirico F, Yildirim M, Ziapour A. Improving health literacy with artificial intelligence. *J Health Soc Sci.* 2023;8(2):95-97. doi: 10.19204/2023/MPRV1.

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